

Protein chemical synthesis combined with mirror-image phage display yields D-peptide EGF ligands that block the EGF-EGFR interaction

Cristina Díaz-Perlas,^[a] Monica Varese,^[a] Salvador Guardiola,^[a] Macarena Sánchez-Navarro,^[a] Jesús García,^[a] Meritxell Teixido*^[a] and Ernest Giralt*^[a,b]

Abstract: The epidermal growth factor (EGF) pathway is overactivated in a number of cancers, being a good target for clinical therapy. Although several drugs targeting the EGF receptor (EGFR) are on the market, tumours acquire resistance very rapidly. As an alternative, small molecules and peptides targeting EGF have been developed although with moderate success. Here we report on the use of mirror-image phage display technology to discover protease-resistant peptides with the capacity to inhibit the EGF-EGFR interaction. After the chemical synthesis of the enantiomeric protein D-EGF, two phage display peptide libraries were used to select binding sequences. The D-versions of these peptides bound to natural EGF, as confirmed by surface acoustic wave (SAW). High-field NMR showed that the best EGF binder, D-PI_4, interacts preferentially with an EGF region that partially overlaps with the receptor binding interface. Importantly, we also show that D-PI_4 efficiently disrupts the EGF-EGFR interaction. This methodology represents a straightforward approach to find new protease-resistant peptides with potential applications in cancer therapy.

Introduction

The development of improved antagonists of growth factors is a key objective in medicinal chemistry. The epidermal growth factor (EGF) is a mitogenic factor that stimulates the proliferation, migration and differentiation of cells.^[1] Several types of solid tumours, such as head and neck, breast, colorectal and non-small-cell lung cancer, present overexpression of EGF and/or its receptor (EGFR).^[2,3] Binding of EGF to EGFR triggers the uncontrolled growth of the tumour cells, which can lead to tumour invasion and metastasis. For this reason, the EGF-EGFR pathway is one of the main focuses for cancer therapy. Several EGFR inhibitors are on the market: i) two monoclonal antibodies (cetuximab and panitumumab) that target the extracellular part of the receptor; and ii) small-molecules (such as gefitinib and erlotinib) that inhibit the cytoplasmic tyrosine-kinase activity of EGFR.^[4–6] Despite the initial success of these drugs for the

treatment of several types of cancer, EGFR mutations greatly affect the efficacy of these treatments.^[7] Hence, EGF has emerged as an alternative target to inhibit the EGF-EGFR pathway, as demonstrated by the positive results obtained by CIMAvax-EGF, a vaccine that induces antibodies against self EGF.^[8] In this sense, we have recently described a family of nanobodies that bind EGF with high affinity and are able to block the EGF-EGFR interaction.^[9]

However, so far, only a limited number of small molecules and peptides (suramin,^[10] cp23G^[11] and _D(CVRAC)^[12]) have been reported but with limited success. This scarcity may be related with the absence of grooves and cavities on the flat surface of EGF, a feature that hinders the identification of binders. Peptides have a higher degree of structural flexibility than small-molecules and can adapt more easily to irregular targets. The EGF-binding peptides discovered until now (cp23G and _D(CVRAC)) relied on the identification of a suitable candidate and its subsequent modification to ensure protease resistance while preserving its activity. In the present work, we directly identified serum-stable peptides able to disrupt the EGF-EGFR interaction through the use of mirror image phage display.

Mirror-image phage display takes advantage of the chirality of amino acids and consequently of the peptides and proteins that they form. Several examples of mirror image phage display have been described identifying ligands for proteins such as VEGF or Src-SH3.^[13–17] In this methodology, the panning experiments are carried out against the mirror-image of the target protein, therefore we first approached the chemical synthesis of the EGF enantiomer (D-EGF).

Results and Discussion

Chemical synthesis of of the enantiomeric D-EGF

EGF is a 53-amino acid long, single-chain protein. The three-dimensional structure of EGF adopts a $\alpha\beta$ -fold stabilised by three intramolecular disulfide bridges.^{[18][19]} Although the chemical production of this natural protein was already described by Moriga and Munekata's groups,^[20–24] the methodology involved the synthesis of nine building blocks and their condensation. In order to develop a simpler and faster synthetic approach, we first explored the potentially simplest strategy based on the stepwise solid-phase peptide synthesis (SPPS) of the full-length protein. However, the low coupling efficiency after the 40th amino acid hampered the achievement of D-EGF (Fig. S1). In addition, we suspected massive aspartimide formation, as the EGF sequence contains two Asp-Gly motifs which frequently undergo this side reaction.^[25,26] To address these issues, we designed a simplified convergent approach than the ones previously described based

[a] Dr. C. Díaz-Perlas, Dr. M. Varese, Dr. S. Guardiola, Dr. M. Sánchez-Navarro, Dr. J. García, Dr. Meritxell Teixido*, Prof. E. Giralt* Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB Barcelona), Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology (BIST), Baldiri Reixac 10, Barcelona 08028, Spain. E-mail: meritxell.teixido@irbbarcelona.org; ernest.giralt@irbbarcelona.org

[b] Prof. E. Giralt* Department of Inorganic and Organic Chemistry, University of Barcelona, Martí I Franqués 1-11, Barcelona 08028, Spain
Supporting information for this article is given via a link at the end of the document.

on only two peptide fragments that could be ligated by native chemical ligation (NCL) and then oxidised to yield the folded protein. This strategy has been followed before for the synthesis of other D-proteins such as HIV-1 protease or VEGF.^[27,28] Previously to the synthesis, we evaluated the suitability of the retrosynthetic disconnection of the 6 Cys residues in the EGF sequence (Fig. S2)^[29,30] and selected Tyr13-Cys14 as disconnection site because it is a priori the most favourable position for NCL.^[31] The two peptide fragments, D-EGF P1 (n1-y13) and D-EGF P2 (I15-r53), were synthesised separately using SPPS (Fig. 1). D-EGF P1 was synthesised using in situ neutralisation Boc/Bzl chemistry and a thioester group was then introduced onto the resin in the form of 3-mercaptopropionic acid. D-EGF P2 was synthesised using Fmoc/tBu chemistry, and the HMPP linker was incorporated onto the resin to provide a carboxylic acid at the C-terminus and the final amino acid was a Cys to enable the NCL (Table S1, S2 and Fig. S3).

A) H-nsdsec(¹)plshdGyc(²)lhdGvc(¹)myiealdky
ac(²)nc(³)vvGyiGerc(³)qyrdlkwwelr-OH

Fig. 1. A) Amino acid sequence of D-EGF, indicating the three disulfide bridges at Cys6-Cys20, Cys14-Cys31 and Cys33-Cys42. B) Schematic representation of the synthesis of D-EGF. Cartoon representation of enantiomeric structure of isolated EGF (PDB file 2KV4).

To obtain the full-length polypeptide, the two fragments, D-EGF P1 and D-EGF P2, were dissolved in ligation buffer (see supplementary information). After 6 h, all the D-EGF P2 was consumed and the ligated protein (reduced D-EGF) was formed as the main product (Fig. S4). Finally, the 6 Cys residues were oxidised with the subsequent folding of the protein. Based on

previous reports,^[32,33] the oxidation was performed by air in the presence of reduced/oxidized glutathione as redox reagent. After 3 days, the change in the retention time and the loss of six units in the mass spectrum indicated completion of the oxidation process (Fig. S4).

Using 1D ¹H-NMR spectroscopy and circular dichroism (CD), we confirmed that the oxidized D-protein was properly folded. The ¹H-NMR spectrum of synthetic D-EGF was practically identical to that of the recombinantly expressed protein composed of L-amino acids (Fig. S5). The high chemical shift dispersion of the ¹H resonances in both spectra is characteristic of well-folded proteins. In addition, D-EGF displayed a CD profile that was the mirror image of that of the recombinant EGF, as expected for two enantiomeric proteins with the same three-dimensional structure (Fig. S6). Importantly, this is the first reported synthesis of EGF requiring the production of only two segments followed by their ligation, making this a shorter and modular synthetic scheme. The application of this new methodology has enabled the production of D-EGF with good yields and purity in a relatively short period of time.

Mirror-image phage display to discover peptide ligands of D-EGF

To find new peptides able to bind EGF and disrupt the EGF-EGFR interaction, we used two commercially available peptide libraries, namely Ph.D.-12 and Ph.D.-C7C (New England Biolabs, Inc.), as the initial pool of peptides. The displayed peptide in the Ph.D.-C7C library are presented to the target as loops of seven residues with two flanking Cys, with a complexity of the order of 10⁹ independent clones. Although in Ph.D.-12 only a tiny fraction of the 4.1 x 10¹⁵ possible 12-mer linear sequences are present, this library can be considered to have equivalent diversity as the Ph.D.-C7C library but spread out over 12 residues. Both libraries were screened against the chemically synthesised D-EGF and after three rounds of panning a ca. 300-fold enrichment of recovered phage was observed for the Ph.D.-12 library while almost no enrichment for Ph.D.-C7C was seen (Fig. S7). Single clones for the 2nd and 3rd round were sequenced (Table S3). The Ph.D.-C7C library appeared to produce few binders for D-EGF, both for the low recovered phage after each round and for the presence of a target-unrelated peptide (TUP).^[34] The sequence analysis of both libraries revealed a high number of clones with some common motif (Fig. S8). Eleven clusters of similar sequences were identified and nine of these sequences were chosen to be further studied (Table 1). In this regard, peptides were selected from both libraries to have more diversified scaffolds of linear and cyclic peptides.

Table 1. Binding affinity values (K_D) for EGF obtained by SAW, protease stability and EGF-EGFR inhibitory activity (IC_{50}) calculated from AlphaScreen for the selected D-peptides. n.d. = not determined; LoD = Limit of detection. Nomenclature is adapted from Spengler *et al.* [35]

Peptide	Phage clone	Sequence	K_D (μM) EGF	K_D (μM) VEGF	Serum stability	IC_{50} (μM) AlphaScreen
D-PI_1	Clone_12_19	H-hwydwvsvlnpa-NH ₂	115 \pm 12	<LoD	> 24h	122
D-PI_3	Clone_12_25	H-hlpfsnswfwvr-NH ₂	217 \pm 13	<LoD	n.d.	n.d.
D-PI_4	Clone_12_39	H-hdwwwinryGkt-NH ₂	54 \pm 2	<LoD	> 24 h	13
D-PI_7	Clone_C7C_14	H-c(&)khsGawsc(&)-NH ₂	310 \pm 20	<LoD	n.d.	n.d.

Protease-resistant D-ligands of EGF

We chemically synthesised the enantiomers (D-peptides) of the sequences previously selected from phage display by Fmoc/tBu SPPS as C-terminal carboxamides (Table S4 and Fig. S9). The affinity of these peptides for EGF was then evaluated using a surface acoustic wave (SAW) biosensor (Fig. S10)^[36]. EGF was immobilised through the side-chains of Lys and peptides were flown over the protein. The binding events occurring on the functionalised surface, which directly affect the acoustic wave parameters of the biosensor, were measured. Four out of the nine sequences interacted with EGF with micromolar affinities (Table 1, Fig. 2a, Table S5 and Fig. S11). Peptides D-PI_1 and D-PI_4 were the ones that displayed higher affinities ($K_D = 115 \pm 12 \mu\text{M}$ and $54 \pm 2 \mu\text{M}$, respectively) with a slightly lower K_D than cp23G, the best binder reported so far.^[11]

To confirm that the interaction of D-PI_1 and D-PI_4 with EGF was selective, control SAW experiments were performed with another growth factor (vascular endothelial growth factor, VEGF). In this case, only weak responses were detected even at the highest peptide concentrations (Table 1 and Fig. S12).

Fig. 2. SAW sensorgrams of D-PI_1 (A) and D-PI_4 (B) injected at various concentrations against immobilised EGF. AlphaScreen based protein-protein interaction inhibition assay for D-PI_1 (C) and D-PI_4 (D).

Fig. 3. Mapping the binding site of the D-PI_4-peptide on EGF. A) Plot of combined NH chemical shift perturbations for each EGF residue upon addition of 10 eq. of D-PI_4 peptide. CSPs greater than the mean value plus one standard deviation (dotted line) were considered significant. B) Expansions of the ¹H-¹⁵N HSQC spectra of ¹⁵N-EGF in the absence (blue contours) and in the presence (red contours) of 10 eq. of D-PI_4 illustrating the chemical shift changes caused by D-PI_4 on selected EGF cross-peaks (labelled with a star in panel A). C) Cartoon representation of the EGF structure in complex with EGFR (PDB code: 1IVO) showing in red those EGF residues with CSPs greater than the mean value plus one standard deviation.

Once we had proved that the D-peptides bind to EGF, we sought to define their binding site on the protein surface. Towards this end, we recorded bidimensional ¹H ¹⁵N-HSQC NMR spectra of ¹⁵N-labeled EGF in the absence and presence of D-PI_1 and D-PI_4 (Fig. 3 and Fig. S13). Addition of D-PI_1 induced small chemical shift changes on the EGF spectra (Fig. S13). The chemical shift changes caused by D-PI_4 were moderate (Fig. 3) and affected those residues located in an EGF region that partially overlaps with the EGF-EGFR interface in the three-dimensional structure of the complex (PDB code 1IVO).^[19] These results

suggest that D-PI_4 may be able to inhibit the interaction between EGF and its receptor.

A major drawback of most therapeutic peptides is their susceptibility to proteolytic degradation, which results in short plasma half-lives and rapid clearance from circulation. Peptides containing D-amino acids, such as the ones developed in this work, represent an effective way to enhance the biostability of these therapeutic agents. As we anticipated, peptides D-PI_1 and D-PI_4 showed a good stability in biological media remained intact for more than 24 h upon incubation with human serum at 37°C (Table 1 and Fig. S14).

D-PI_4 disrupts the EGF-EGFR interaction

The selected peptides were further evaluated for their ability to inhibit the EGF-EGFR interaction, a feature required for their therapeutic application. For this purpose we used the AlphaScreen assay, in which two binding partners (in our case EGF and EGFR) are captured on donor and acceptor beads. The interaction brings the beads in close proximity and laser excitation causes the energy transfer from one bead to the other, ultimately producing a fluorescent signal (Fig. S15). Inhibitors of this biomolecular interaction will lead to a reduction in the AlphaScreen signal. When both proteins were pre-incubated with D-PI_1 and D-PI_4 a concentration dependent decrease in fluorescent was observed (Fig. 2C and 2D) demonstrating that these D-peptides disrupt the formation of EGF-EGFR complex with IC_{50} values in the micromolar range (Table 1). D-PI_4 emerged as the best candidate, with strong inhibitory activity ($IC_{50}=13 \mu\text{M}$). These results are in agreement with D-PI_4 being the strongest EGF binder in the SAW experiment ($K_D=54\pm 2 \mu\text{M}$ for EGF) and with the NMR experiments which suggested that D-PI_4 binds to biologically relevant epitopes of EGF. To the best of our knowledge, D-PI_4 is the peptide with the best inhibitory capacity of EGF-EGFR interaction and the highest EGF binding affinity described to date.

Conclusions

In this work, we have designed and developed a new synthetic approach combining for the first time SPPS and NCL to chemically synthesise D-EGF. The successful synthesis allowed the panning of two phage display peptide libraries, yielding several clones with the capacity to bind to the target protein. The synthesis of the D-versions of these peptides followed by the evaluation of their EGF binding capacity revealed D-PI_4 as the best peptide candidate. Remarkably, this protease-resistant peptide was able to disrupt the protein-protein interaction between EGF and EGFR at low micromolar concentrations. This work expands the use of mirror-image phage display as a source of protease-resistant ligands for challenging drug targets as is EGF, which could potentially find application as new targeted anti-cancer agents.

Experimental Section

Panning against immobilised D-EGF

The protein (D-EGF) was coated onto microtiter wells. 7.5 μg of protein dissolved in 150 μL of sodium bicarbonate (0.1 M NaHCO_3 , pH 6) were immobilised on 96-well microtiter plates (96 well EIA/RIA plates, Corning) overnight at 4°C with gentle agitation in a humidified container. Wells were blocked with blocking buffer (0.1 M NaHCO_3 , 5 mg/mL BSA, pH 8.6) for 1 h at RT and washed 6 times with TBST (TBS + 0.1% [v/v] Tween-20).

Two phage libraries (Ph.D.TM-C7C and Ph.D.TM-12 Phage Display Peptide Library) were incubated with the immobilised target in 100 μL of TBST, phage input was 10¹¹ plaque forming units (pfu). After 1 h at RT, wells were washed 10 times with TBST. Phage were eluted with 100 μL of elution buffer (0.2 M Glycine-HCl, 1 mg/mL BSA, pH 2.2) for 10 min with gentle agitation and neutralised with 15 μL of neutralisation buffer (1 M Trizma base, pH 9.1). The elution and neutralisation step were repeated three times. 200 μL of the recovered phage were amplified as described before.

The second and third rounds of panning were carried out in a similar way. The phage input was maintained at 10¹¹ pfu and the percentage of Tween in TBST was raised to 0.3% [v/v]. Purification of phage particles and sequencing of phage single-stranded DNA were performed as described before.

Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) experiments

Sam5 Blue biosensor (SAW-Instruments, Bonn, Germany) was used to measure the sensograms. It is composed of a biosensor unit, an autosampler and a microchip module with a gold layer sensing surface on a quartz chip. The chip was cleaned and functionalised with 16-mercaptohexanoic acid to form a self-assembled monolayer (COOH-SAM). EGF was immobilised by carboxyl-group activation with a 1:1 mixture (v/v) of (1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-carbodiimide (EDC) (200 mM) and N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) (50 mM). Then, a solution of EGF (15 μM) in 150 μL of PBS was added to the chip. Finally, the capping of the unreacted positions was performed with a solution of ethanolamine (1 M, pH 8.5). Peptides affinities were calculated with several injections of a range of concentrations (0.1 – 300 μM) at 25°C. Between injections HCl (0.1 M, pH 1) was added to regenerate the chip. The Origin Pro 7.5 software was used to calculate the binding curves. And the Fit Master software was used to calculate the K_D through a non-linear fit of the data using the following formula:

$$A_{eq} = \frac{c}{c + K_D}$$

where A_{eq} is the association equilibrium and c the concentration of the ligand. For a schematic representation of the experiment see Fig. S13.

Nuclear magnetic resonance

NMR experiments were carried out at 25°C on a Bruker Avance III 600 MHz spectrometer equipped with a TCI cryoprobe. Data processing was performed using TopSpin 3.0.

EGF samples (final protein concentration 50 μM) were dissolved in NMR buffer: 20 mM sodium phosphate (pH 6.8), 50 mM NaCl

FULL PAPER

and 0.01% (w/v) NaN_3 , supplemented with 10% D_2O . 4,4-dimethyl-4-silapentane-1-sulfonic acid (DSS) was used as an internal chemical shift reference.

Water suppression in the monodimensional ^1H NMR experiments was achieved using the Watergate method.^[37]

^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectra of ^{15}N -labelled EGF (50 μM) in the absence and presence of the selected peptides (0.5 mM) were acquired to identify the peptide binding region on EGF using the amide backbone assignment previously reported.^[18] HSQC experiments were acquired with 128x2048 complex points with a total of 8 transients per increment. Combined NH chemical shift perturbations ($\text{CSP} = [(\Delta\delta\text{N}/5)^2 + (\Delta\delta\text{H})^2]^{1/2}$) were plotted for each protein residue; only CSPs greater than the mean value plus one standard deviation were considered significant.

Protein-protein interaction inhibition assay using AlphaScreen technology

AlphaScreen assays were performed in a final volume of 50 μL in 96-well Optiplates (PerkinElmer) (Fig. S4). 10 μL of EGF (His-tag functionalised, 3 nM final concentration in PBS pH 7.4 buffer, 0.1% BSA, 0.1% Tween-20) and 10 μL of peptide (at different concentrations) were incubated at RT for 15 min. Next, 10 μL of EGFR-Fc (10 nM final concentration in the same buffer) were added and incubated at RT for 30 min. Then, 10 μL of anti-His Acceptor beads (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ final concentration) were added and incubated at RT for 60 min. 10 μL of Protein A Donor beads (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ final concentration) were added to each well and incubated for 30 min in the dark. The fluorescence reading was performed in a EnVision® Multilabel Reader (emission at 615 nm). Dose-response curves were obtained with the GraphPad Prism 7 software, using non-linear fit and variable slope, from which IC_{50} and Hill slope values were calculated. Experimental Details.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by MINECO-FEDER (BIO2016-75327-R), the Generalitat de Catalunya (XRB and 2017SGR0998) and with the support of LCF/PR/GN14/10270002 - "la Caixa" Foundation. We thank the NMR facility from Scientific and Technological Centre of the University of Barcelona (CCiT-UB). IRB Barcelona is the recipient of a Severo Ochoa Award of Excellence from MINECO (Government of Spain) and the CERCA Programme of the Catalan Government.

Keywords: EGF; EGFR; Mirror Image Phage display; Protein-protein interaction; Peptide inhibitor.

- [1] R. W. C. Wong, L. Guillaud, *Cytokine Growth Factor Rev.* **2004**, *15*, 147–156.
 [2] M. K. Nicholas, R. V. Lukas, N. F. Jafri, L. Faoro, R. Salgia, *Clin. Cancer Res.* **2006**, *12*, 7261–7270.
 [3] G. Karpel-Massler, U. Schmidt, A. Unterberg, M.-E. Halatsch, *Mol. Cancer Res.* **2009**, *7*, 1000–1012.
 [4] B. You, E. X. Chen, *J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2012**, *52*, 128–155.
 [5] C. Yewale, D. Baradia, I. Vhora, S. Patil, A. Misra, *Biomaterials* **2013**, *34*, 8690–8707.
 [6] A. Russo, T. Franchina, G. R. Rita Ricciardi, A. Picone, G. Ferraro,

- M. Zanghi, G. Toscano, A. Giordano, V. Adamo, *Oncotarget* **2015**, *6*, 26814–26825.
 [7] C. R. Chong, P. A. Jänne, *Nat. Med.* **2013**, *19*, 1389–1400.
 [8] P. C. Rodríguez, X. Popa, O. Martínez, S. Mendoza, E. Santiesteban, T. Crespo, R. M. Amador, R. Fleytas, S. C. Acosta, Y. Otero, et al., *Clin. Cancer Res.* **2016**, *22*, 3782–3790.
 [9] S. Guardiola, M. Varese, M. Sánchez-Navarro, C. Vincke, M. Teixidó, J. García, S. Muyldermans, E. Giral, *Angew. Chemie - Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 13843–13847.
 [10] R. J. Coffey Jr., E. B. Leof, G. D. Shipley, H. L. Moses, *J. Cell. Physiol.* **1987**, *132*, 143–148.
 [11] S. Guardiola, J. Seco, M. Varese, M. Díaz-Lobo, J. García, M. Teixido, L. Nevola, E. Giral, *ChemBioChem* **2018**, *19*, 76–84.
 [12] M. Cardó-Vila, R. J. Giordano, R. L. Sidman, L. F. Bronk, Z. Fan, J. Mendelsohn, W. Arap, R. Pasqualini, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2010**, *107*, 5118–5123.
 [13] D. M. Eckert, V. N. Malashkevich, L. H. Hong, P. A. Carr, P. S. Kim, *Cell* **1999**, *99*, 103–115.
 [14] S. A. Funke, D. Willbold, *Mol. Biosyst.* **2009**, *5*, 783–786.
 [15] K. Mandal, M. Uppalapati, D. Ault-Riché, J. Kenney, J. Lowitz, S. S. Sidhu, S. B. H. Kent, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2012**, *109*, 14779–14784.
 [16] M. Uppalapati, D. J. Lee, K. Mandal, H. Li, L. P. Miranda, J. Lowitz, J. Kenney, J. J. Adams, D. Ault-Riché, S. B. H. Kent, et al., *ACS Chem. Biol.* **2016**, *11*, 1058–1065.
 [17] K. Wiesehan, D. Willbold, *Chembiochem* **2003**, *4*, 811–5.
 [18] H.-W. Huang, S. K. Mohan, C. Yu, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* **2010**, *402*, 705–710.
 [19] H. Ogiso, R. Ishitani, O. Nureki, S. Fukai, M. Yamanaka, J. H. Kim, K. Saito, A. Sakamoto, M. Inoue, M. Shirouzu, et al., *Cell* **2002**, DOI 10.1016/S0092-8674(02)00963-7.
 [20] H. Yajima, K. Akaji, N. Fujii, K. Hayashi, K. Mizuta, M. Aono, M. Moriga, *J. Chem. Soc. Chem. Commun.* **1984**, 556, 1103–1105.
 [21] S. Y. Shin, Y. Kaburaki, M. Watanabe, E. Munekata, *Biosci. Biotech. Biochem.* **1992**, *56*, 108–112.
 [22] S. Y. Shin, Y. Kaburaki, M. Watanabe, E. Munekata, *Biosci. Biotech. Biochem.* **1992**, *56*, 399–403.
 [23] S. Y. Shin, Y. Kaburaki, M. Watanabe, E. Munekata, *Biosci. Biotech. Biochem.* **1992**, *56*, 404–408.
 [24] S. Y. Shin, M. Shimizu, T. Ohtaki, E. Munekata, *Peptides* **1995**, *16*, 205–210.
 [25] R. Subirós-Funosas, A. El-Faham, F. Albericio, *Tetrahedron* **2011**, *67*, 8595–8606.
 [26] E. Nicolás, E. Pedroso, E. Giral, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1989**, *30*, 497–500.
 [27] S. Kent, Y. Sohma, S. Liu, D. Bang, B. Pentelute, K. Mandal, *J. Pept. Sci.* **2012**, *18*, 428–436.
 [28] L. Zhao, W. Lu, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2014**, *22*, 56–61.
 [29] T. M. Hackeng, J. H. Griffin, P. E. Dawson, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **1999**, *96*, 10068–10073.
 [30] T. Kimmmerlin, D. Seebach, *J. Pept. Res.* **2005**, *65*, 229–60.
 [31] P. E. Dawson, T. W. Muir, I. Clark-Lewis, S. B. H. Kent, *Science* **1994**, *266*, 776–778.
 [32] J. Y. Chang, P. Schindler, U. Ramseier, P. H. Lai, *J. Biol. Chem.* **1995**, *270*, 9207–9216.
 [33] J. Y. Chang, L. Li, P. H. Lai, *J. Biol. Chem.* **2001**, *276*, 4845–4852.
 [34] W. D. Thomas, M. Golomb, G. P. Smith, *Anal. Biochem.* **2010**, *407*, 237–240.
 [35] J. Spengler, J. C. Jiménez, K. Burger, E. Giral, F. Albericio, *J. Pept. Res.* **2005**, *65*, 550–555.
 [36] S. Guardiola, M. Díaz-Lobo, J. Seco, J. García, L. Nevola, E. Giral, *ChemBioChem* **2016**, *17*, 702–711.
 [37] M. Liu, X. Mao, C. He, H. Huang, J. K. Nicholson, J. C. Lindon, *J. Magn. Reson.* **1998**, *132*, 125–129.

FULL PAPER

Entry for the Table of Contents

FULL PAPER

Mirror image phage display to discover new protease-resistant peptides able to disrupt the interaction between EGF and EGFR

Cristina Díaz-Perlas,^[a] Monica Varese,^[a] Salvador Guardiola,^[a] Macarena Sánchez-Navarro,^[a] Jesús García,^[a] Meritxell Teixidó^{*[a]} and Ernest Giralt^{*[a,b]}

Page No. – Page No.

A peptide designed by mirror-image phage display disrupts the interaction between EGF and EGFR